

Terrorism Activities as Threat to Political Instability and Its Effect on Economic Development in Sub-Saharan Africa: An Empirical Study Using Panel Multiple Regression and Panel Generalized Linear Model

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Yao Hong Xing* ⁽²⁾Winfred Addy Okoe ⁽³⁾Felix Kwame Nyarko ⁽⁴⁾Haris Muhammad ⁽⁵⁾Jean-Jacques Dominique Beraud ^{(1) (2) (3) (4) (5)}School of Economics and Finance, Jiangsu University, 212013, China

Corresponding Author's Email: addywinfred@gmail.com

Abstract

The study assesses the effect of terrorism which causes political instability on economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. The study uses panel data of 33 Sub-Saharan countries from 2000 to 2014. The study used panel data methodologies such as multiple regression methods and generalized linear models. The study concluded that political instability directly affects economic development and any potential rise in political turmoil in any Sub-Saharan African country will lead to a negative effect on their economic development. In conclusion, the act of terrorism and violence causing political instability hampers the peace and tranquility of a country and also retard growth as well as development. Therefore, it will be paramount and pertinent for governments to ensure peace prevails in their respective countries to promote social and economic development.

Keywords: Political Instability; Foreign Direct Investment; Economic Development; Corruption; Rule of Law

Introduction

Terrorism is the premeditated use or threat of use of violence by individuals or subnational groups to obtain a political or social objective through the intimidation of a broad audience, beyond that of the immediate victim. Although the motives of terrorists may differ, their actions follow a standard pattern with terrorist incidents assuming a variety of forms: airplane hijackings, kidnappings, assassinations, threats, bombings, and suicide attacks. Terrorist attacks are intended to apply sufficient pressure to a government so that it grants political concessions. If a besieged government views the anticipated costs of future terrorist actions as greater than the costs of conceding to terrorist demands, then a government will make some accommodation. However, a cogent terrorist body can, in principle, reach its objective quicker if it is able to enhance the effects of its campaign. These aftermaths can assume many systems including casualties, property destructions, a heightened level of anxiety, and untold economic costs. According to Kunreuther et al. (2003) in 2016 the act of terrorism and its impact on the world economic outlook was somewhat lower than 2015 although the cost to the world economy stood at US\$84 billion. However, a vivid observation of terrorism and its impact on the world economy is smaller as compared to other broader forms of violence because of its significant impact. Notably, the cost of terrorism in 2016 reached a whopping \$14.3 trillion which is about one percent of the total cost of violence. Moreover, the rate of terrorism is conventional; the strategies of security agencies and the costs to counter such menace do not take into the substantial impacts on business and investment. Additionally, terrorism is one of the kinds of violence where the costs that are associated with restraints are likely to exceed its substantial costs. However, while the economic impact of terrorism is small it is still critical to contain it as it has the potential to spread quickly and with major social ramifications. The act of terrorism has a tendency to potentially impose some costs on a country that is targeted through a number of ventures. There are economic costs that arise as a result of terrorism such as foreign direct investment (FDI) reduction, infrastructure destruction, allocating of funds for public investment to security operations and trade limitation. The results of terrorism in a country through which FDI is diverted experience reduced economic growth. Economic turmoil through civil war just drives away capital inflows through FDI from a country (Collier et al., 2003) in effect the act of terrorism vastly reduces capital and investment inflows (Enders & Sandler, 1996). Activities of terrorism have become pressing issues and challenges for policymakers in both developing and developed countries. The act of terrorism has increasingly gained attention in Africa which has been receiving exceptional attention with regards to counter-terrorism (Abrahamsen, 2004; Colliers, 2003). Scores of literature have highlighted the act of terrorism which

gained attention in the late 1980s with likes of Sudan, Burundi, Liberia and D.R. Congo experienced some terrorists' activities and casualties which resulted in the loss of lives and the destruction of properties (Colliers, 2004). For instance, about 4,993 acts of terrorism cases were recorded in Sub-Saharan Africa between 1974 and 2008 (Elu & Price, 2012). Terrorism at one breadth is fueled by extremist religious beliefs. Abrahamsen (2004) claims that the operatives of counter-terrorism in Africa by the British found that there are enormous Muslims in Africa as compared to the Middle East which may heighten the propensity of extremist Islamist terrorism (Elu, 2012). The US Department of Home Land Security has responded to this challenge by implementing changes and tighter security to counter with domestic terrorism possibly catalyzed by extremist Islam. However, international terrorism, and in particular African terrorism, continues to juxtapose a challenge to counter-terrorism policy.

Upon sober reflections on these challenges which are development threatening motivates this study to assess the extent at which terrorism through violence and political instability affect economic development in the Sub-Saharan African region. The study intends to contribute to existing and ongoing literature on terrorism and its effect on economic development to shape policy direction and academic discussions.

The organization of the study can be found as; part one introduces the study, part two presents the data and the methodology of the study, part three presents the empirical findings and discussion and part four concludes the study.

Data and Methodology

Data

The study sourced its data from World Development Indicators and Worldwide Governance Indicators from the period of 2000 to 2014 on a panel of 33 Sub-Saharan African countries. The study considered five variables to examine the effect of terrorism or political instability on economic development. However, the independent variable for the study is political stability score which represents the perception that people hold to the extent at which there are violence and act of terrorism, etc. and the dependent variable is gross domestic product per capita which measures the total production of goods and services in a given period of time divided by the total population of a country. In order to control for the effect of political instability on economic development, some variables like corruption, the rule of law and foreign direct investment are chosen as control variables. Foreign direct investment is measured by the total inflows of foreign direct investment in a given year, corruption is measured by the perception to an extent at which there is an evidence of corruption in a country and the rule of law is measured by the extent at which law enforcement agencies and legal implementations are embarked on. The rule of law, political stability and corruption are measured by scores where -2.5 mean weak and +2.5 means strong.

Methodology

The study employed a panel study methodologies to achieve its objective of investigating the effect of terrorism on economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. The methodologies adopted for the study can be expressed as; panel unit root test, panel correlation matrix, panel co-integration test, panel multiple regression, panel generalized linear model and granger causality test.

In the first instance, the study performed a unit root test to identify the stationary status of the variables in order not to perform bogus regression. Perhaps, the null hypothesis of unit root test affirms that there is an evidence of unit root in the variables. However, after the outcome of the unit root test has been proven it is expected that the null hypothesis should be rejected. The tests of Levin et al. (2002), Im et al. (2003) and Maddala & Wu (1999) are considered for testing for a unit root in the variables. Subsequently, the need arises for the second test, thus correlation matrix; this test is performed to unravel the truth whether there is an existence of multicollinearity in the independent variables. The rule of thumb for the multicollinearity test posits that no two

independent variables should have coefficients of $-/+0.70$ to be highly correlated with the dependent variable. After it has been confirmed that there is no problem with multicollinearity then the study performs a co-integration test to confirm the long run relationship between the independent and the dependent variables. Evidence of the co-integration relationship will ensure the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no co-integration relationship between the independent and the dependent variables.

Most importantly, the next step paves the way for the study to perform the regression analysis to find out the extent to which terrorism through political instability affects economic development and foreign direct investments. The first regression method to be used is the multiple regression method; this method is considered due to its multiple functions of taking effect multiple independent variables and it is the study’s main regression method. However, to be able to confirm the robustness of the results of the multiple regression method, the generalized linear model is chosen for a robust check. Lastly, the study intends to find out the causal relationship between the independent and the dependent variables; the granger causality test will be performed to find the direction of causality either unidirectional or bidirectional.

Model specification

The econometric model considered for the study can be written as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 X_1)_{it} + (\beta_2 X_2)_{it} \dots + (\beta_k X_k)_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \tag{1}$$

In equation (1), β_0 stands for constant that is the base line for economic development, $\beta_1 X_1 \dots \beta_k X_k$ represents the independent variables thus political instability, foreign direct investment, the rule of law and corruption, Y represents the dependent variable thus economic development, ϵ represents the error term or stochastic disturbances, i represents the cross-section of 33 Sub-Saharan countries and t represents the time period of 2000 to 2014.

$$\ln gdp_{it} = f(\text{polstab}, \ln fdi, \text{rulelaw}, \text{corco})_{it} \tag{2}$$

In equation (2), $\ln gdp_{it}$ represents economic development (gross domestic product per capita), polstab represents political instability (terrorism activities), $\ln fdi$ represents foreign direct investments, rulelaw represents the rule of law and corco represents corruption. Foreign direct investment and gross domestic product per capita were taken into their natural logarithm to avoid fluctuation in the data series and also to make them absolute values.

Empirical findings and discussion

Summary Statistics

Table 1 displays the summary statistics of the variables used for the study. From the table, it can be reported that the average growth rate of gross domestic product per capita for Sub-Saharan Africa annually stood at 7.134% from the period of 2000 to 2014 and the minimum and the maximum growth rate were 5.267% and 9.920% respectively. The act of terrorism and violence through political instability had an average score of -0.438 annually with a maximum score of 1.118 and a minimum of -2.477. Foreign direct investment for the sample period grew at an annual rate of 1.892% with minimum growth of -3.823% and a maximum of 21.134%. See table 1 for more details.

Table 1 Summary statistics

	lngdppc	polstab	rulelaw	corco	lnfdi
Mean	7.134	-0.438	-0.534	-0.555	1.892
Median	6.896	-0.250	-0.517	-0.600	2.489
Maximum	9.920	1.118	1.077	1.217	21.134
Minimum	5.267	-2.477	-2.009	-1.773	-3.823

Std. Dev.	1.143	0.808	0.592	0.552	1.624
Skewness	0.607	-0.434	0.098	0.527	2.800
Kurtosis	2.257	2.501	3.126	3.328	41.712
Jarque-Bera	41.840	20.696	1.125	25.123	31556.660
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.570	0.000	0.000
Observations	495	495	495	495	495

Panel Unit Root Test

The study performed a unit root test to find out the stationary status of the variables to be able to carry on its regression analysis. Therefore, the tests of Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC), Im-Pesaran & Shim (IPS), Maddala & Wu (ADF-Fisher and PP-Fisher) were performed and the results can be found in table 2. From the table, it is evidenced that all the variables were stationary at level form because all the tests performed should significance with the exception of lngdppc which did not show significance with IPS and ADF-Fisher tests but at first difference, all the variables showed significance in all the tests. Therefore, the study can confirm that there is no evidence of unit root in the variables at the first difference. Moreover, the variables are stationary hence the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 2 Unit Root Tests

	lngdppc	polstab	lnfdi	rulelaw	corco
Level form					
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-4.119***	-8.096***	-3.665***	-14.967***	-32.022***
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	2.359	-6.480***	-2.363**	-11.328***	-13.966***
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	64.878	173.463***	99.985**	221.689***	224.600***
PP - Fisher Chi-square	90.799**	198.199***	97.032**	225.015***	186.935***
First difference					
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-13.605***	-24.950***	-20.227***	-26.851***	-29.109***
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-10.216***	-21.419***	-17.042***	-31.578***	-31.314***
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	232.672***	420.581***	354.162***	567.393***	558.720***
PP - Fisher Chi-square	264.972***	514.394***	461.815***	622.079***	615.639***

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level. lngdppc represents economic development, polstab represents terrorism/political instability, rulelaw represents the rule of law, corco represents corruption, lnfdi represents a foreign direct investment. Foreign direct investment and gross domestic product per capita are in their natural logarithm.

Correlation Matrix

The study at this stage computed the correlation matrix with the objective of checking for multicollinearity in the variables. The rule of thumb avers that no two independent variables should be highly correlated with the dependent variable at a coefficient of $-/+0.70$. Table 3 below exhibits the outcome of the correlation matrix and from the table; it can be found that there is no evidence of multicollinearity. The highest coefficient in the table can be reported as 0.330 thus political instability. Moreover, political instability, the rule of law and corruption showed positive and 1% significant correlation with economic development whiles foreign direct investment showed a negative and 1% significant correlation with economic development.

Table 3 Correlation matrix

Correlation	lngdppc	polstab	rulelaw	corco	lnfdi
Probability	1				
lngdppc	1				
polstab	0.330***	1			
rulelaw	0.248***	0.671***	1		
corco	0.163***	0.579***	0.879***	1	
lnfdi	-0.157***	-0.11**	-0.018	0.037	1

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level. *Lngdppc* represents economic development, *polstab* represents terrorism/political instability, *rulelaw* represents the rule of law, *corco* represents corruption, *lnfdi* represents a foreign direct investment. Foreign direct investment and gross domestic product per capita are in their natural logarithm.

Co-Integration Test

To ascertain the long run relationship that exists between the dependent and the independent variables in order to estimate the long run coefficients; the study employed Johansen Fisher panel cointegration test to that effect. Table 4 displays the outcome of the cointegration test and it can be reported that at none there was no cointegration relationship but at most 1 to at most 4, there is an evidence of cointegration relationship hence there is a long run relationship existing between the dependent and the independent variables. All results of the trace test and max-eigen test are all significant at a 1% significance level from at most 1 to at most 4.

Table 4 Co-Integration test

Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test							
Included observations: 495							
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue)							
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*				Fisher Stat.*		
No. of CE(s)	(from trace test)	Prob.	sig.	(from max-eigen test)	Prob.	sig.	
None	42.980	0.980		61.400	0.569		
At most 1	351.000	0.000	***	351.000	0.000	***	
At most 2	538.400	0.000	***	538.400	0.000	***	
At most 3	445.300	0.000	***	357.900	0.000	***	
At most 4	242.500	0.000	***	242.500	0.000	***	

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level

Assessing the Effect of the Act of Terrorism through Political Instability on Economic Development in Sub-Saharan Africa

Act of terrorism through violence and political instability has been rampant in Sub-Sahara Africa and this menace seems to suppress the growth of the economies of countries under the Sub-Saharan region. The study aims to assess the effect this menace as on the economic development of the region. However, the study considered two regression methods to analysis its data to make robustness and statistically significant inference. The results of the analysis can be found in table 5. From the table, it can be reported that political instability has a direct and positive effect on economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. With a coefficient of 0.385 at a 1% significance level, a percentage increase in the act of terrorism or political instability will lead to a decrease in economic development at 0.385%. In reverse, a percentage increase in political stability by controlling or getting rid of terrorism will lead to a 0.385% increase in economic development. Foreign direct investment which is one of the drivers of economic growth shows an inverse relationship with economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa confirming that a percentage increase in foreign direct investment will lead to a 0.080% decrease in economic development. The rule of law which can be explained as the extent to which legal institutions and law enforcement agencies are independent of political interference to work diligently to ensure equity by apply laws enacted seems to have a positive and direct effect on economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. However, a percentage increase in strengthening the rule of law processes and procedures will lead to a 0.470% increase in economic development. Corruption which is widely considered as a canker and growth retard ingredient confirms an inverse effect on economic development per the outcome of the study's analysis. It will be imperative for governments with the Sub-Saharan Africa region to tighten and intensify their efforts of curbing corruption because an increase in corrupt practices will lead to a decrease in economic development by 0.424%.

To support or robust check the results of the multiple regression method, the study used a generalized linear model to perform that function and from table 5, the results of the generalized linear model report the same results of the multiple regression method. Therefore, the study can robustly infer the results that it is statistically significant.

Table 5 Results of Regression Analysis

Variable	Main Multiple Regression		Robust check Generalized linear Model	
	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Coefficient	z-Statistic
polstab	0.385	(4.75) ***	0.385	(4.75) ***
lnfdi	-0.080	(-2.65) **	-0.080	(-2.65) **
rulelaw	0.470	(2.51) **	0.470	(2.51) **
corco	-0.424	(-2.31) **	-0.424	(-2.31) **
c	7.469	(82.83) ***	7.469	(82.83) ***
Rquared	0.135			
Fstatistics	19.085***			
Log likelihood			-732.185	
LR statistic			76.339***	
obs.	495		495	

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level. *lngdppc* represents economic development, *polstab* represents terrorism/political instability, *rulelaw* represents the rule of law, *corco* represents corruption, *lnfdi* represents a foreign direct investment. Foreign direct investment and gross domestic product per capita are in their natural logarithm.

Granger Causality Test

The study employed the granger causality test to ascertain the order of causality either unidirectional or bidirectional between the dependent and the independent variables. Table 6 shows evidence of granger causalities which are unidirectional. From the table, there is no evidence of bidirectional causality between the dependent and the independent variables. The evidence of unidirectional granger causality can be found from political instability to economic development, foreign direct investment to economic development, the rule of law to political instability and corruption to political instability. The unidirectional granger causality simply means that there is a causal relationship from the first variable to the latter but not vice versa. However, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no evidence of granger causality among the variables.

Table 6 Granger Causality Test

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	sig.
polstab does not granger cause <i>lngdppc</i>	429	3.308	0.038	**
<i>lngdppc</i> does not granger cause polstab		0.903	0.406	
rulelaw does not granger cause <i>lngdppc</i>	429	2.165	0.116	
<i>lngdppc</i> does not granger cause rulelaw		0.670	0.513	
corco does not granger cause <i>lngdppc</i>	429	1.931	0.146	
<i>lngdppc</i> does not granger cause corco		0.440	0.644	
lnfdi does not granger cause <i>lngdppc</i>	429	9.607	0.000	***
<i>lngdppc</i> does not granger cause lnfdi		0.747	0.474	
rulelaw does not granger cause polstab	429	12.639	0.000	***
polstab does not granger cause rulelaw		1.409	0.246	
corco does not granger cause polstab	429	7.031	0.001	***
polstab does not granger cause corco		0.050	0.951	
lnfdi does not granger cause polstab	429	0.222	0.801	
polstab does not granger cause lnfdi		0.587	0.556	
corco does not granger cause rulelaw	429	0.696	0.499	
rulelaw does not granger cause corco		1.979	0.140	
lnfdi does not granger cause rulelaw	429	1.929	0.147	
rulelaw does not granger cause lnfdi		0.145	0.865	
lnfdi does not granger cause corco	429	1.427	0.241	
corco does not granger cause lnfdi		0.855	0.426	

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level. *Lngdppc* represents economic development, *polstab* represents terrorism/political instability, *rulelaw* represents the rule of law, *corco* represents corruption, *lnfdi* represents a foreign direct investment. Foreign direct investment and gross domestic product per capita are in their natural logarithm.

Conclusion

The study assessed the effect of terrorisms through political instability on economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa for the period of 2000 to 2014 on a panel study of 33 Sub-Saharan African countries. The study used secondary data sourced from World Development Indicators and Worldwide Governance Indicators. Moreover, the study was a panel study hence the use of panel data methodologies such as unit root test, correlation matrix, co integration test, multiple regression method, generalized linear model and granger causality test.

After the analysis of the data, the study found that the act of terrorism which causes political instability through violence has a direct effect on economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. However, there is an inverse effect or relationship between foreign direct investment and economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. By strengthening the processes and procedures of the rule of law have a positive and direct effect on economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. Perhaps, the independence of the judicial system, police administration, and proper implementation and law enforcements will lead to a strong and positive increase in economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. But with political interference in the rule of law through corrupt practices weakens economic development which one way or the other suppresses the right processes to economic development.

In conclusion, the act of terrorism and violence causing political instability hampers the peace and tranquility of a country and also retard growth as well as development. Therefore, it will be paramount and pertinent for governments to ensure peace prevails in their respective countries to promote social and economic development.

Acknowledgment

This paper is supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (Number 71701082 and 71271103)

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